

PLEASE Strategy Based on Product Approach (PSBPA) to Enhance Students' Achievement in Writing Descriptive Text

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ABSTRACT: Modifying a couple of method can cover their weaknesses each other. This current research aims to intently find out if there is a significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through PLEASE strategy based on Product approach. This is a quasi-experimental research design that conducts a quantitative method. The students were gave writing tests, namely pre-test and post-test. There are 23 students in a class. The students are given treatments with the strategy namely PLEASE based on an approach namely product approach (PSBPA). The data are statistically analyzed through paired sample t-test in SPSS version 22 to obtain the findings. The finding shows that there is a significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through PLEASE strategy based on Product approach. The score of post-test (73.46) is higher than pre-test (56.91). The *t*-value, which is 14.071 is higher than the *t*-table, which is 2.074 with the sig (2-tailed) is 0.000 which is lower than 0.05. It is suggested for teachers to apply this new strategy at class, because it can boost the students' writing ability, especially in descriptive text. Teacher should integrate PLEASE strategy in teaching writing for other text types and use model texts to guide writing tasks. And for further researchers should explore the strategy's impact on different age groups or other types of writing.

KEYWORDS: Descriptive text, PLEASE strategy, Product approach, Stage, Writing achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Writing is a quite complicated ability. There are difficulties based on learners' experiences in acquiring writing caused by several factors related to lack of ideas. The learners are often confused to express their idea at the beginning of writing. The learners have difficulties in producing and organizing ideas, creating sentences with a good grammar and constructing the text based on the structure systematically. Yates, et al. in Ramos, et al. (2020) define writing problems as those related to the deviation from the grammar, syntax (sentence, construction), and meaning of a target language; they are divided into surface problem, which refers to grammar, and global problem, which refers to meaning, to cohesiveness, and to organization. Learner should understand the grammar and word order to transfer the meaning of the message in their readable form.

Therefore, to overcome the problem above, there should be an effort to enhance learners' writing skill by creating, applying, developing, or modifying a good strategy in teaching writing skill. One of the solutions is the implementation of PLEASE Strategy. Cited in Rahmalia, et al. (2022), PLEASE strategy is a paragraph-writing strategy developed by addressing writing deficits that students with disabilities frequently made. PLEASE strategy is a mnemonic strategy to remember to employ the six steps including of pick the topic, list the ideas about the topic, evaluate, activate, supply, end used to help students to understand what they want to write.

Based on Akincilar in Rahmalia, et al. (2022), the procedures of PLEASE are: 1) Pick: the first step of the mnemonic reminds students to pick the topic, audience and type of the paragraph they plan to write; 2) List: reminds students to generate list of ideas that they want to include in their writing; 3) Evaluate: students evaluate their list to see if it is complete or it is necessary to add more ideas. After that, they sequence or organize the ideas; 4) Activate: students activate the paragraph by constructing a topic sentence and ask the students to write the first sentence about the topic; 5) Supply: students supply sentences that support the topic sentence by using their list of ideas. They are expected to turn each idea into a sentence and elaborate on it where appropriate; 6) End: the final step of mnemonic reminds the students to end their writing with a conclusion. Students also expected to evaluate their

work by revising their ideas and editing their mistakes. This strategy is believed to be a suitable way to stimulate the learners' ability to enhance their writing skill. PLEASE strategy can help the learners how to start their writing and it is suitable for all of genres/kinds of paragraph. The strategy provides a structure to help students generate and organize ideas and to write sentences and paragraphs. This strategy is useful to help the students that have many problems in writing because it provides cues to help students remember and apply activities involved in the process of planning and writing.

Several previous studies have proven the effectiveness of PLEASE Strategy to teach writing in teaching EFL learners. Aminatun, et al (2018) found that PLEASE Strategy was more effective than Guided Writing Strategy to teach writing. Al- zu'bi, et al. (2019) found that PLEASE strategy affected paragraph writing positively. Liza (2013) found that PLEASE strategy helps the students organize and generate their ideas easily. This strategy also makes students active and feel motivated in writing. Russaifa, et al. (2021) concluded that PLEASE strategy could improve students writing skill, this method could solve the students' problem in writing, the students felt motivated and gave positive response towards the implementation of the method.

Even though several previous studies have been conducted in investigating the effectiveness of using PLEASE Strategy in teaching writing of EFL learners, they still limited in the learning activity that only focuses on process of writing without paying attention to the result of writing. It can be seen from the result of the studies which shows that the students still have many errors in grammar and mechanics. So, even producing more sentences in their text, but the text cannot be understood easily. A previous study done by Richards, et al. (2002) showed that the difficulty of writing lies not only in generating and organizing ideas, but also in translating their ideas into readable text. Hence, it needs to explore the implementation of PLEASE Strategy to create a more helpful learning writing skill. It also provides benefit not only interesting during the learning process and even after the learning process in writing activities. Additionally, it shows that the modification of this strategy is needed.

In this case, the researcher aims to develop PLEASE Strategy based on product approach to support this strategy so it can be applied more helpful in teaching writing skill. The role of product approach in PLEASE Strategy is as the systematic guidance for learners to create a good text during writing process. Nunan in Bloushi (2024) said that the product-based approach, the focus is more on the final product of the paper which should be text free from errors. Students provide a transformed text imitating a model text the teachers had provided them. The product-based approach means that teachers are simply leading the students to the final product of their essay; on the contrary, the process-based approach emphasizes on the thorough steps taken in the process to produce any English text.

Principally, product approach is an approach that focuses on the form. Badger, et al. in Eliwanti, et al. (2017) clarify that product-based approaches see writing as mainly concerned with knowledge about the structure of language. The product approach can be comprehended as the approach of writing where the focus is on generating grammatically correct structures, imitating the native model of composition and the generation of higher order composition skills such as writing paragraphs. In addition, the approach does not pay much attention to the communication, audience, or the composition skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Byrne (1988:1) states that writing is clearly much more than the production of graphic symbols, just as speech, it is more than the production of sounds. The symbols have to be arranged, according to certain conventions, to form words, and words have to be arranged to form sentences. In addition, Hyland (2003:3) defines writing as a product constructed from the writer's command of grammatical and lexical knowledge, and writing development is considered to be the result of imitating and manipulating models provided by the teacher. It can be inferred that writing is the skill to deliver information through written language. The product of writing is the construction of language units from the smallest to the larger forms which has to be accepted with the rule of language itself.

Writing aspects are important to consider to create an effective and communicative writing. Heaton (1988:146) states five aspects of writing in a rating scale that indicates:

1) Content

The scoring of the content depends on the students' capability to write their ideas and information in the form of logical sentences.

2) Organization

The organization refers to the students' capability to write their ideas and information in such a good logical order, with the topic and supporting sentences clearly stated.

3) Vocabulary

The scoring of vocabulary depends on the students' capability to use words or idioms to express idea logically.

4) Language Use

Language use refers to the competence in writing sentences, whether simple, complex, or compound, correctly and logically. It also refers to the ability to use the correct arrangement in sentences and to include elements such as nouns, adjectives, and time signals

5) Mechanics

The score for mechanic depends on the students' competence to write spelling, punctuation, capitalization, paragraphing, and hand writing whether or not can be read.

Furthermore, there are different approaches to teach writing. One of the earliest approaches is product-based approach as stated by Tangpermpoon in Pasand, et al. (2013), students will start from pre-writing to composing and to correcting. In this approach what is emphasized is raising students' awareness, especially in grammatical structures. Product writing is an approach to teach writing that focuses on students' final production, that is, the text the students are asked to produce.

The product approach forces the writer to concentrate on the finished text, or the product of writing, rather than on the steps and stages necessary to arrive at that product. Finishing the piece quickly, efficiently and in one sitting is what counts. According to Nunan in Pasand, et al. (2013), in this approach, the focus is on the final product which should be a coherent, error-free text and students will initiate, copy, and transform models provided by textbooks or by teachers.

By adopting a product approach to writing, it is believed that teachers can help learners develop an awareness of discourse and grammar. This might support the students to be a proficient and independent writer. Moreover, as product writing focuses on the end product, it is probably less time consuming. Honestly, this research aims to modify PLEASE strategy based on product approach in order to support this strategy to be applied appropriately in all of writing aspects.

Steele in Hasan, et al (2010) states that product-based approach comprises of four stages :

1. Students study model texts and then the features of the genre are highlighted.
2. This stage consists of controlled practice of the highlighted features, usually in isolation.
3. This is the most important stage where the ideas are organized. Those who favor this approach believe that the organization of ideas is more important than the ideas themselves and as important as the control of language. The students are planning, noting, and outlining their ideas to write their own descriptive text.
4. This is the end product of the learning process. Students choose from the choice of comparable writing tasks. To show what they can be as fluent and competent users of the language, students individually use the skills, structures and vocabulary they have been taught to produce the product.

In order to support this strategy that can be applied and solve students' problems in each writing process by providing imitating form. The used product approach involves in steps of PLEASE strategy. Therefore, the elaboration of modified PLEASE strategy based on product approach is below.

1. Pick: the teacher asks the students to pick a topic for their paragraph.

Pick, Stage 1

- a) The teacher and the students discuss the topics that are going to be used.
- b) The teacher gives model text to the students and asks the students to observe and analyze the text.

2. List: The teacher asks the students to list the idea of the topic.

List, Stage 2

- a) Identifying the topic by outlining the facts and related information of the topic.
- b) The teacher generates the students to practice making an appropriate sentence by using the information in outline.

3. Evaluate: The students look over their list to ensure that it contains all fact or relevant ideas to the topic and add or delete information if necessary.

Evaluate, Stage 2

- a) The students do peer-correction to check their list of information and give feedback to their friends.
4. Activate: The students activate their paragraph by writing a topic.
Activate, Stage 3
 - a) The students organize the main idea for every paragraph in the form of sentence.
5. Supply: The teacher asks the students to supply and construct sentences to support the main idea that they have constructed before.
Supply, Stage 3
 - a) The students produce sentences based on teacher's paragraph as model.
6. End: The students write a concluding sentence and edit the sentences in their paragraph.

This literature review supports the way this research was conducted.

METHODOLOGY

To answer the formulated research questions, the researcher conducted a quantitative study in the form of one-group pre-test-post-test design.

Figure 1. Research Design

The figure above illustrates that pre-test is administered before the treatment to obtain information about the students' writing achievement which is prior to the treatment. The researcher then gives the treatments which entail teaching writing through the modified PLEASE strategy at one class. Afterward, a post-test is given to see the difference of students' writing achievement as a result of the treatments.

PARTICIPANTS

Sample of this research is one class of the 7th grade in one of Junior High School in Lampung province that consisted of 23 students. It was known that the students of the class had low score in writing. They seemed to be in the beginner level of English.

INSTRUMENTS

The students were required to write a descriptive text about a famous person individually based on five provided topics (as a pre-test and post-test). The students had 90 minutes to write at least two paragraphs. According to Oshima (2007: 61), descriptive writing appeals to the senses, so it tells how something looks, feels, smells, tastes, and/or sounds. The students' writing was scored by using rating scales of writing assessment adapted from Heaton (1988) in order to have construct validity. Using this writing assessment scale, the students' writing was scored based on each writing aspect (content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanics) by two raters, i.e. the researcher and one of the English teachers of that school. In testing the reliability of the writing test, inter-rater reliability was used.

DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher collects the data with an instrument, i.e. writing test. The test is administered at the beginning as the pre-test and at the end as the post-test. The tests are the same. The students are asked to describe the physical appearance and the personality of one of famous people in Indonesia. In this case, the researcher scored the students' writing in accordance with some aspects of writing adapted from Heaton (1988).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research question is : 'Is there any significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through PLEASE strategy based on Product approach ?'. The researcher calculated the data of the post-test and pre-test. Through

paired sample t-test, the data were truly computed to seek whether there is a significant difference in the students' writing achievement of the students who are taught through the modified PLEASE strategy based on product approach. The following tables are the result of the Paired Sample T-Test.

Table 1. Paired Sample T-Test

		Paired Differences			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Mean	Error	Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Post-test - Pre-test	16.54348	5.63857	1.17572	14.10518	18.98178	14.071	22	.000

From the table above, the post-test and the pre-test are compared. The post-test is higher than the pre-test. The mean difference is 16.54 with the t-value of 14.071 at the sig (2-tailed) of 0.000. It is lower than 0.05. It can be concluded that there is a significant increase in the post-test towards the pre-test. The hypothesis (H₁) is then accepted. Equally, it proves that there is a significant improvement in students' writing achievement after the students are taught through PLEASE strategy based on Product approach. Based on the findings of this research, there was a significant improvement in the students' writing achievement after the students were taught through PLEASE strategy based on product approach. The results indicate that it affects in various aspects, which are content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanics.

The improvement of writing occurred because the modified strategy was integrated with an approach that complete the weakness of the original strategy. PLEASE strategy deals with the process, while product approach deals with the result. It is a perfect combination. By matching the strength of PLEASE strategy which is according to Rahmalia, et al. (2022) who said that PLEASE strategy has good result in teaching writing, with the strength of product approach which is supported by Badger, et al. in Eliwarti (2017) that says, "product-based approach sees writing as mainly concerned with knowledge about the structure of language", a way-out would be existing.

When PLEASE strategy was applied at class, it made the process of learning activities, especially in making descriptive texts went smoothly. Moreover, the models of descriptive text that the researcher gave to the students during the learning process boosted the students' ability in writing. It was because they looked at the result of the process in making the text. They saw the result as a model of the text. The finding in research question 1 concluded that the modified strategy can enhance students' writing ability, especially in writing descriptive texts.

When students were asked to describe something or someone, they were provided several celebrities and famous people in the world. It eased the process of writing that the students did, because the objects were familiar with them. Liza (2013) found that PLEASE strategy would help the students organize and generate their ideas easily. Product approach succeeded cover the weakness of PLEASE strategy, which is it still had limited activity to solve students' entire problem in producing paragraph with grammatical correct. And through this modified strategy, everything could be covered.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The students go through the learning process with the modified PLEASE strategy based on product approach. The integration of the two methods, i.e. PLEASE strategy and product approach, brings positive impact in enhancing students' writing achievement. It statistically proves that there is a significant improvement in the post-test compared to the pre-test in students' writing achievement in descriptive text. The product approach covers the weakness of the original PLEASE strategy. Moreover, the students feel more

understanding the materials, especially in the language use by looking at the model of text. They develop their writing aspects. Finally, they increased their achievement of writing ability, especially in descriptive text.

Teachers should apply this modified method in a class since this new method is simple and does not need extra tools. That is a very good choice to boost students' writing achievement, especially in descriptive text. Since PLEASE strategy deals with the process and product approach concerns with the result, a great increase in writing skill will be obtained. Teacher should apply this new modified PLEASE strategy in teaching writing for other text types and use model texts to guide writing tasks. This research was conducted only in a certain condition of one of Junior High School in Lampung Province, so the results of the current research cannot be generalized. But, this research could be a reference for further researchers who want to conduct similar research. The further researchers should explore the strategy's impact on different age groups or other types of writing.

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